

VARIABILITY, CORRELATION and PATH ANALYSIS RELATED to YIELD CONTRIBUTING TRAITS in the BC₁F₂ POPULATION of GROUNDNUT (*Arachis hypogaea*. L)

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Abstract

The present investigation was done in the BC₁F₂ population of the cross between TMV 7 and ICG 15419. Genetic variability parameters were assessed for eight biometrical traits namely, plant height, number of primary branches, pod length, pod width, hundred pod weight, hundred seed weight, oil content and pod yield per plant. The highest PCV and GCV were observed in the number of primary branches and the traits, plant height, pod width and hundred pod weight exhibited moderate estimates of PCV and GCV. Among other pod-related traits, hundred pod weight exhibited both a positive correlation and a positive direct effect with pod yield per plant and hence this trait can be emphasised during selection.

Keywords: Groundnut, variability, correlation, path analysis and backcross.

I.Introduction

Tetraploid cultivated groundnut is one of the chief sources of oil predominantly cultivated in Gujarat, Andhra Pradesh and Tamil Nadu. It is also one of the cheapest sources of vegan protein. Present-day groundnut, *Arachis hypogaea* (2n=2x=40) is the product of a cross between two diploid parents *Arachis duranensis* (2n=2x=20) and *Arachis ipaensis* (2n=2x=20) [1]. Though being a native of Brazil, groundnuts are now spread in several parts of the world with varied uses such as for direct consumption, for the production of peanut butter, and peanut flour and also for other confectionery items. Currently, the world is moving towards a vegan lifestyle and peanut milk could be a potential replacement for vegans and also for lactose intolerant people with extremely nutritional benefits.

Groundnut, being a multi-utility crop, improving the yield and quality of the produce relies upon the hands of a plant breeder. Being a crop with a narrow genetic base due to polyploidization, the variability naturally present is also very less [2] and therefore it is crucial to create or increase the variability which can be brought about by recombination breeding. Recombination breeding aids in the development of a wide range of segregants, which can be a source of variation, and strict selection procedures must be utilised during selection without affecting the plant's overall output. Despite finding new sources of variation, it will be meaningful only if it is heritable because only such traits would be passed on from one generation to the next and therefore it is essential to assess the heritability of each trait along with estimating the percentage of variation. This study mainly focuses on estimating the genetic variability parameters, heritability and the relationship between pod-related traits in the BC₁F₂ population of groundnut.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant materials

The present investigation was carried out at V.O.C Agricultural College, Killikulam. A medium oleic genotype, ICG 15419 and TMV 7 were obtained from ICRISAT and oilseed research station, Thindivanam respectively for developing a back cross population. TMV 7 is an agronomically elite low oleic variety and a back cross programme was framed to introgress the genes responsible for oleic acid from ICG 15419 into TMV 7. Hybridization was done in a crossing block and the F_1 was generated. These plants were genotyped with allele-specific primers to confirm the true hybrid nature. The confirmed F_1 plants were backcrossed with the recurrent parent TMV 7 to develop BC_1F_1 . The BC_1F_1 plants were also genotyped with the same allele-specific primers in the following season and the confirmed plants were selfed to develop BC_1F_2 generation.

Data collection and statistical analysis

Observations were recorded for pod-related traits on each BC_1F_2 plant for pod length, pod width, hundred pod weight, hundred seed weight, oil content and pod yield per plant. Mean, range, standard deviation, genotypic and phenotypic variances [3] genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV & GCV) [4], 1953), heritability [5] and genetic advance [3] were calculated using Microsoft Excel. Correlation coefficients were computed using GRAPES, an online R-based tool [6] and the path analysis was carried out using PB-Perfect, an online R-based tool for plant breeding [7].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Variability

Predicting the mean performance would aid in selecting genotypes that outperform the others in terms of yield, other favourable features, and adaptability [8]. It was observed that most of the inbred lines had better performance for all the traits than the mean. Next to mean performance, the success of a cross depends on the variability present between the parents and also on the variability created in the segregating population. Variations can be observed at both phenotypic and genotypic levels and importantly, environment also plays a crucial role in deciding the magnitude of variability. Due to ceaseless selection, the intrinsic variability has succumbed to depletion and a need arises to create variability which can be attained by adopting a simple recombination breeding programme [9]. The phenotypic and genotypic coefficient of variation of the traits under study are furnished in **Table 1**. It was evident from the results that the phenotypic coefficient of variation was found to be greater than the genotypic coefficient of variation for all the traits and it was observed that the difference between PCV and GCV was more in pod yield per plant indicating that this particular trait was comparatively highly influenced by the environment. The trait, number of primary branches exhibited the highest PCV and GCV and the traits, plant height, pod width, and hundred pod weight exhibited moderate estimates of both PCV and GCV. Similar results for number of primary branches was recorded by [10,11]. Pod length, hundred seed weight and oil content exhibited low PCV and GCV values which was in accordance with [12,13] for oil content.

Heritability and genetic advance

The precision of any field trial depends on the traits possessing high heritability because it is the only part that gets transferred to the offspring from parents [14]. The gain obtained out of selection for a trait which is termed as genetic advance is equally important to estimate the final outcome of the selection. Hence, the estimates of heritability combined with high or moderate genetic advance would help in differentiating the traits with

additive and non-additive effects and therefore make the selection procedure successful. From **Table 1** it was found that the traits, plant height, number of primary branches, pod width and hundred pod weight exhibited higher estimates of both heritability and genetic advance as per cent of mean indicating additive gene effects, making the selection fruitful. Parallel findings for plant height and primary branches were reported by [15]; for hundred pod weight by [16,17] and for low GCV estimate in oil content was reported by [17]. It was also evident from the results that the trait pod length, hundred seed weight and pod yield per plant had higher and moderate estimates of heritability and genetic advance as per cent of mean respectively. Oil content had higher heritability but low genetic advance as per cent of the mean (**Fig.1**).

Correlation

Simultaneous selection of traits can be achieved by correlation where the correlation coefficients explain the direction of the relationship between any two traits and such trait pairs can be improved concurrently. If the correlation coefficient is +1, it denotes a positive correlation and if it is -1, it denotes a negative correlation indicating that improving one trait has an opposite effect on the other and a correlation coefficient of zero indicates no correlation between the trait pair. In this study, a significant positive correlation was observed between plant height (0.269) and the number of primary branches; plant height (0.223) and pod width; and between pod width (0.248) and hundred seed weight (**Fig.2**). With the trait, pod yield per plant, hundred pod weight (0.301) exhibited a significant positive correlation and the result was in accordance with [18]. It is evident from the results that genotypes with higher hundred pod weight have the potential of producing more pods thereby increasing the yield of the groundnut plant which would be economically more profitable for the farmers.

Path analysis

Selection is a process where several traits are analysed to understand their gene action which takes a lot of time. Path analysis enables a plant breeder to focus on traits (independent) which have a positive direct effect on the total yield (dependent) and ignore the ones which have a negative effect, thereby reducing the time drastically [19]. Direct effects are the ones when there are no intervening variables between them and indirect effects are the ones where one variable affects another through an intermediary variable. The details of the direct and indirect effects of pod-related traits on the pod yield per plant are furnished in **Table 2**. It was observed from the results that the trait hundred pod weight had a positive direct effect on pod yield per plant indicating that this trait can be used as a selection criterion in groundnut breeding programmes. From the results of path analysis, the residual effect was 0.482 and the total variability in the BC₁F₂ population was 51.8%.

IV.CONCLUSION

Based on the current findings, the traits plant height, number of primary branches, pod width, and hundred pod weight were the traits causing heritable variation in the population under study. Additionally, the trait, hundred pod weight exhibited a positive correlation and also a positive direct effect on the pod yield per plant and hence selection based on the trait, hundred pod weight indicates better nutrient use efficiency leading to better quality seeds, thereby ensuring a higher yield eventually fetching higher prices in the market.

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TABLE 1

GENETIC VARIABILITY PARAMETERS FOR THE EIGHT TRAITS IN THE BC₁F₂ POPULATION OF TMV 7 AND ICG 15419

	Mean	Min	Max	PCV	GCV	Heritability	GAM
PH	47.85	24.00	68.00	16.53	15.93	92.97	31.65
PB	9.16	3.00	16.00	32.68	32.03	96.11	64.70
PL	2.46	2.00	2.90	9.06	8.75	93.31	17.41
PW	1.26	0.80	1.60	13.62	12.83	88.73	24.90
HPW	66.04	47.37	90.94	13.31	12.92	94.25	25.84
HSW	27.97	24.45	35.14	7.47	7.31	95.81	14.74
OC	49.50	44.26	53.48	4.19	3.91	87.12	7.51
PYP	22.02	14.08	26.96	11.77	9.50	65.24	15.81

(PH-Plant height, PB-Number of primary branches, PL-Pod length, PW-Pod width, HPW-Hundred pod weight, HSW-Hundred seed weight, OC-Oil content and PYP-Pod yield per plant; PCV-Phenotypic coefficient of variation, GCV-Genotypic coefficient of variation, GAM-Genetic advance as per cent of mean)

Fig.1. Bar chart depicting the percentage of heritability and genetic advance as per cent of mean

Fig.2. Correlogram of the eight traits under study

TABLE II

DIRECT AND INDIRECT EFFECTS OF THE EIGHT TRAITS IN THE BC₁F₂ POPULATION OF TMV 7
AND ICG 15419

Traits	PH	PB	PL	PW	HPW	HSW	OC	PYP
PH	0.045	-0.015	0.003	0.007	0.016	-0.002	0.004	0.058
PB	0.012	-0.055	0.004	0.004	0.014	-0.004	0.006	-0.019
PL	-0.001	0.001	-0.143	0.000	0.042	-0.006	0.003	-0.102
PW	0.010	-0.007	0.000	0.031	0.021	-0.009	-0.002	0.044
HPW	0.002	-0.002	-0.019	0.002	0.326	-0.001	-0.008	0.301*
HSW	0.002	-0.006	-0.023	0.008	0.007	-0.037	0.004	-0.046
OC	-0.003	0.006	0.009	0.001	0.053	0.003	-0.052	0.017

Residuals : 0.482

(PH-Plant height, PB-Number of primary branches, PL-Pod length, PW-Pod width, HPW-Hundred pod weight, HSW-Hundred seed weight, OC-Oil content and PYP-Pod yield per plant)